

CLASSIFICATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6470838>

Shukhratova Zebo Shavkat qizi

Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute 1st year student of Master's degree

Scientific supervisor: Sadullayeva Nilufar Azimovna

Abstract: *Phraseological units can be classified according to their various features from the point of view modern linguistics. Phraseological units are divided into categories according to their etymological, structural-semantic, motivational level meaning, accordingly, which word group they are represented by in linguistic works. The fund of Uzbek phraseology is replete with national and borrowed, terminological and non-terminological units as phraseology in English language.*

Key words: *Phraseological units, structural-semantic, motivational level meaning, terminological, non-terminological units.*

In Uzbek linguistics, the classification of phraseological units proposed by – scholars. According to their classification, all phraseological units are subdivided into phraseological adhesions, phraseological unity and phraseological combinations (Jabborova, 2020). Vinogradov (1997) writes that phraseological adhesions are such semantically indivisible phrases in which the integral meaning is completely inconsistent with the individual meanings of the words that make them up.

Phraseological unit is semantically indivisible and integral phraseological word, the integral semantics of which is motivated by the individual meanings of their constituent words, for example: gap talashmoq, (to wrangle), zimdan kuzatmoq (to observe).

Phraseological combinations are such phrases in which there are words, both with free and associated usage, for example: qiyomatli do'st (tru friend), tishini oqini ko'rsatmoq (to smile).

In English, these three types include the following phraseological units.

1. Phraseological adhesions have the greatest cohesion of components that lose their lexical meaning, which is absorbed by the meaning of the entire phraseologism. These units, such as spik and span, to out off with a shilling, to talk through one's hat, make up the most common group.

2. Phraseological units make up a larger group. They differ in terms of their mobility and their meaning is determined by the meaning of their components. Such phraseological units can include the following examples: to take (lay) hold of, as busy as a bee, to draw the line.

3. Phraseological combinations differ from the units in that one of the constituent components is used in its direct meaning. Combinations make up the most numerous group. These include expressions such as to strike (to deal, to inflict) a blow, to break a promise (an agreement, a rule). The components of phraseological combinations are more independent than with adhesions.

From the point of view of linguistic stylistics, phraseological units in the Uzbek and English languages are also usually classified depending on their place in the scale of stylistic colors.

The phraseological turns of the modern Uzbek fictional language can be divided into three large categories: interstyle phraseology, colloquial phraseology and book phraseology.

Interstyle phraseological phrases are understood as stable combinations of words that are known and used in all styles of the language and therefore represent phraseological units with a “zero” stylistic features, for example: so’zini ustida turmoq (keep one’s word), chin ko’ngildan (sincere/ly).

Phraseological units of a colloquial differ from interstyle phraseological units in a narrower sphere of use (these are phraseological phrases, mainly used in oral speech) on the one hand, and with its specific “lowered” expressive-stylistic coloring, on the other hand. For example: olovga moy quymoq (add fuel to the fire).

In English, there are:

1. Phraseologisms of high stylistic tonality:

(a) archaisms, i.e. phraseological units out of use, for example: Mahomet’s coffin, to meet one in the Duke’s walk;

(b) book-literary phraseological units, for example: Attic salt, the debt of Nature;

(c) foreign origin phraseological units used in English, for example: ab ovo usque ad mala (L. - from the beginning to the end), a chaque saint sa chandelle (Fr. - to every saint his candle).

2. Phraseologisms of the reduced stylistic tonality:

(a) familiar in spoken speech, for example: alive and kicking, sell your as;

(b) professional, for example: a blow job, a loss leader;

(c) vulgar, for example: to hop the twig, to get in a bate.

3. Phraseologisms are stylistically neutral, i.e. appropriate in any speech field of communication. For example: a man in the street, for better and for worse.

Such phraseological units, which have lost their image, devoid of strong stylistic coloring, still retain their ability to act as an expressive means.

So, the stylistic coloring of the lexico-phraseological units of the language is not something constant, unchanged in time; just like other linguistic phenomena, it is mobile and constantly changing. So, scientific and technical terms can be included in everyday life style; vulgar vocabulary can lose its stylistic coloring and penetrate into the literary-familiar substyle, and “situationalism” sometimes get widespread use in everyday speech, etc. Therefore, when translating a literary text, it is necessary to take these phenomena into account (Normurodov, 2020).

The translation of phraseological units is carried out in the following ways:

1. By using equivalents, i.e. phraseological units that completely coincide in languages, for example: to cross the Rubicon – Rubikonni kesib o'tmoq, to shed the crocodile tears – timsoq ko'z yoshlarini to'kmoq. Equivalents can be absolute or relative. For example, absolute: to cast a glance – nazar tashlamoq, the bitter truth – achchiq haqiqat; relative: grass widow – somon odam, proud horse – manman odam.

2. By using of a phraseological analogue (variant), for example: to work one's fingers to the bones – tinimsiz ishlamoq, to pull foot – tezda qochib qolmoq.

3. By using calques, for example: to keep a dog and bark oneself – it ushlamoq lekin o'zi akillamoq, love me, love my dog – meni sevsang kuchigimiham sevasan.

4. By using a descriptive translation, for example: horse and foot – bor kuchi bilan; a skeleton in the cupboard / closet – boshqalardan yashirilgan sir.

In linguistics, phraseologisms are classified according to the construction, etymological, structural-semantic, which part of the sentence they can be in the sentence, motivational level of meaning according to which word group it is expressed. Although phraseology is recognized as a separate science from the point of view of modern linguistics, it is developing in direct connection with lexicology, grammar, stylistics, phonetics, history of language, history of philosophical sciences, logic and geography. Phraseological units as units that are readily stored in a language are always units that have a clear meaning, a constant content, and a structure. When it comes to the phraseological fund of a language, linguists emphasize that their connection to tradition and stability are stable units in both quantity and quality.

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